

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CANCER AND MAJOR METABOLIC RISKS

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Abstract

Cancer and metabolic syndrome (MetS) are major public health concerns, both with increasing prevalence. This study investigates the relationship between major metabolic risks (hypertension - HTN, diabetes mellitus - DM, obesity) and cancer incidence in a sample of 120 patients diagnosed with six common cancer types in the Republic of Moldova (breast, lung, gastric, colon, renal, skin cancer). A retrospective analysis revealed a significant association between metabolic syndrome and the studied cancers, with a higher prevalence of metabolic comorbidities in gastric cancer (85%) and colon cancer (60%) compared to breast cancer (45%), lung cancer (25%), and skin cancer (10%). Patients over 60 years old had the highest rates of HTN (89.9%), DM (75.5%), and obesity (69.4%). Chronic inflammation, observed in 95.7% of patients, plays a central role in carcinogenesis. These findings highlight the importance of monitoring and managing metabolic risk factors for cancer prevention and treatment.

Keywords: cancer, metabolic syndrome, hypertension, diabetes, obesity, inflammation, tumor progression

Introduction

Cancer is one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide, accounting for millions of deaths annually. In 2021, cancer caused 1.15 million deaths in the EU, representing 22% of the total mortality, ranking second after cardiovascular diseases. In five EU countries (Belgium, Denmark, France, the Netherlands, and Spain), it is the leading cause of death [7]. Cancer development is a complex process influenced by both internal and external factors. Internal factors include an individual's genetic constitution, whereas external factors involve exposure to chemicals, radiation, and viral infections [1], [5]. Apart from genetic predisposition, approximately 44% of cancer cases are influenced by modifiable risk factors, including lifestyle habits, environmental exposure, and occupational hazards [2]. Epigenetics involves heritable gene expression changes without altering DNA sequence, including DNA methylation, histone modification, and non-coding RNA regulation. ROS and RNS activate DNMT1, leading to hypermethylation of tumor suppressor gene promoters, reducing their expression and promoting cancer. Additionally, ROS-induced global hypomethylation causes genomic instability and mutations. Abnormal promoter methylation of tumor suppressor genes is a key trigger in tumor development [4]. Among these modifiable factors, metabolic risks play a crucial role in cancer development and progression.

Latent cancer cells exist in everyone, but a healthy body has mechanisms capable of effectively controlling carcinogenesis [3]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), metabolic risk factors include HTN, obesity/overweight, hyperglycemia, and hyperlipidemia. Globally, HTN is the most significant metabolic risk factor, contributing to 19% of total mortality, followed by hyperglycemia and obesity [8]. Metabolic syndrome may also indicate the presence of other cancer risk factors, such as reduced physical activity, excessive intake of high-calorie foods, high-

fat consumption, insufficient fiber intake, and increased oxidative stress [6].

In recent years, studies have demonstrated that individuals with metabolic risks frequently exhibit pro-thrombotic and pro-inflammatory states, facilitating the progression of cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, and certain types of cancer [2]. Furthermore, meta-analyses and prospective cohort studies have established a consistent link between metabolic syndrome and an increased risk of developing various cancers in adults [1].

Given the growing burden of cancer, this study aims to identify significant modifiable risk factors that could be addressed to mitigate the impact of cancer at global, regional, and national levels.

The purpose of the study: This study aims to synthesize current literature and analyzed data regarding the relationship between cancer and major metabolic risks, assessing their impact on cancer incidence and progression to develop efficient prevention and management strategies.

Materials and methods: This study was conducted on a randomly selected sample of 120 patients, with an equal number (n=20) for each of the six most common cancer types in the Republic of Moldova:

- 20 patients with breast cancer
- 20 patients with lung cancer
- 20 patients with gastric cancer
- 20 patients with colon cancer
- 20 patients with renal cancer
- 20 patients with skin cancer

Data were collected from the Republic of Moldova's CANCER-REGISTRY from 2021-2023, selecting patients with confirmed diagnoses based on their medical records. The collected data were entered into Excel, including details such as patient name, gender, residence, date of diagnosis, comorbidities, and

metabolic indices (blood glucose, BMI, blood pressure).

Research Methods

- **Historical Method:** A retrospective analysis of cancer patients from 2021-2023 was performed to evaluate the relationship between major metabolic risks and disease progression.

- **Comparative Method:** Comparison of the six cancer types based on the presence of obesity, DM, and HTN to highlight differences and analyze their influence on cancer development.

- **Descriptive Epidemiology Method:** Detailed description of patient characteristics, including age, gender, geographical location, and metabolic syndrome components.

- **Statistical Method:** Calculation of relevant statistical indicators such as the prevalence of metabolic risks based on age, gender, and cancer type. The proportion of patients with multiple risks was determined, and their correlation with cancer type was assessed.

- **Mathematical Method:** Calculation of simple arithmetic means for key variables such as patient age, blood pressure values, BMI, and blood glucose levels.

Results

Of the total 120 patients, 79 (66%) lived in rural areas, while 41 (34%) resided in urban areas. There was a slightly higher prevalence of female patients (n=66, 55%) compared to males (n=54, 45%), likely due to differential exposure to metabolic risks such as obesity and diabetes.

Prevalence of Metabolic Risks Among Cancer Patients

- **HTN was the most common metabolic risk factor**, present in 86 patients (71.67%), followed by DM in 78 patients (65%) and obesity in 77 patients (64.17%).

- **Metabolic risk factors varied by cancer type:** Gastric cancer patients had the highest prevalence of metabolic comorbidities (85%), followed by colon cancer (60%), breast cancer (45%), lung cancer (25%), and skin cancer (10%).

- **Age-based distribution of metabolic risks:**
 - <50 years: HTN (50%), DM (43.8%), Obesity (31.3%)
 - 50-60 years: HTN (71.8%), DM (56.4%), Obesity (46.2%)
 - 60 years: HTN (89.8%), DM (75.5%), Obesity (69.4%)

Figure 1. Prevalence of Metabolic Risks by Age Group.

These findings underscore the increasing burden of metabolic risks with aging and their potential role in cancer progression.

Conclusions

1. Major metabolic risk factors (HTN, DM, obesity) promote tumor progression through chronic inflammation and oxidative stress.

2. Metabolic risks are unevenly distributed among different cancer types, with gastric and colon cancers showing the highest prevalence of these comorbidities.

3. Cancer patients over 60 years old present the highest accumulation of metabolic comorbidities, with HTN (89.9%), DM (75.5%), and obesity (69.4%).

4. Patients with multiple metabolic comorbidities are most frequently diagnosed with gastric (85%) and colon cancer (60%), compared to breast (45%), lung (25%), and skin cancer (10%).

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